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for large-scale HVDC interconnection and wind integration] (TS-
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List of Abbreviations

CO	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission
LA	Lab Access
UG	User Group
UP	User Project
GFM	Grid Forming
GFL	Grid Following
FRT	Fault Ride Through

Executive Summary

The integration of large-scale offshore wind farms with High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) interconnections is vital to achieving global energy transition targets. However, the complex dynamics of these systems—especially when configured as multi-infeed AC offshore islands—pose significant challenges during transient disturbances such as AC and DC faults. Traditional methods fall short in addressing stability and control in such multi-infeed HVDC environments.

To address this gap, a coordinated control strategy has been developed to enhance transient stability and system resilience. The strategy incorporates advanced control functions, including Fault Ride Through (FRT) capability, active power-frequency (P/f) droop control, and a central master controller. These elements work together to enable fault tolerance, manage power imbalances, and optimize post-fault recovery through dynamic adjustment of control set-points.

This novel approach has been validated through comprehensive simulations in PSCAD/EMTDC, demonstrating strong performance across a range of fault scenarios. Building on these promising results, the **TS-HVDC** project—led by Manchester Metropolitan University (MMU) WSP, and Barcelona Tech (UPC)—aims to experimentally validate the strategy using hardware-in-the-loop testing at TECNALIA's laboratories.

Key aspects of the project include:

- Coordinated control of HVDC interconnectors and offshore wind farms to ensure robust system response and recovery under various fault conditions, including both AC and DC disturbances.
- Validation of the proposed control strategy through both detailed simulation studies and hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing, leveraging TECNALIA's state-of-the-art laboratory facilities.

The project's outcomes are expected to offer crucial insights and practical guidelines for the future design and operation of resilient multi-infeed offshore energy systems, enabling secure and reliable integration of renewable energy at scale.

1 Lab-Access User Project Information

1.1 Overview

The project titled “TS-HVDC – Transient stability enhancement of multi-infeed AC offshore islands for large-scale HVDC interconnection and wind integration” has been hosted at TECNALIA and been conducted during the access period [12 January 2025 – 24 January 2025]. The user group consisted of experts from WSP, Manchester Metropolitan University (MMU), and BarcelonaTech (UPC).

TS-HVDC aimed to experimentally investigate the operation of multi-infeed AC offshore islands, integrating various HVDC interconnectors and offshore wind farms, especially under various fault scenarios. The project focused on the validation of a novel control approach that orchestrates HVDC links and wind farms for effective fault management. The latter focuses on the determination of the control objectives for the fault-ride-through (FRT) control, and the implementation of a coordinated control strategy utilised to dispatch the appropriate control setpoints (active/reactive power and control mode setpoints) for maintaining system operability during disturbances. Emphasis is given on the different control objectives between grid-following (GFL) and grid-forming (GFM) inverters of the HVDC stations, particularly considering their rated capacities. The effectiveness of the proposed approach has already been validated through offline simulations considering case studies on a realistic network with three HVDC links, capable of operating in both GFM and GFL modes, and two wind farms in GFL mode developed in electromagnetic transient (EMT) simulation software. Building on this, TS-HVDC has been carried out hardware-in-the-loop laboratory validation using TECNALIA’s advanced infrastructure. The findings and proposed approach are expected to provide essential guidance for controlling and operating multi-infeed AC offshore islands in the future power system scenario.

1.2 Research Motivation, Objectives, and Scope

The TS-HVDC project was motivated by the growing complexity and urgency of ensuring stability and reliable control in emerging multi-infeed AC offshore islands, which are expected to play a critical role in the future decarbonised power system. These offshore grids typically integrate multiple HVDC interconnectors and offshore wind farms, relying on a mix of GFM and GFL converters. These configurations face challenges such as dynamic interactions between the converter-based units, making the system particularly vulnerable under abnormal conditions such as AC and DC faults. The key challenges addressed by TS-HVDC were the transient stability and post-fault recovery of such systems—areas where significant knowledge gaps remain in current research and operational practice.

Additionally, TS-HVDC was driven by its potential to enable the realisation of robust multi-infeed AC offshore islands that can significantly increase the reliability and flexibility of electricity networks in Europe. Successful implementation of advanced control strategies in these systems can support higher penetration of renewable energy sources (RES), reduce the cost of electricity for consumers, and facilitate a fair and sustainable energy transition. For example, in the UK, these advancements could contribute to a complete decarbonisation of the power sector, a projected 48% reduction in electricity prices, and the creation of up to 1.18 million new jobs in the energy industry. Furthermore, the project’s findings contribute to broader policy and regulatory developments by providing practical solutions aligned with the objectives

of the Holistic Network Design (HND) and the UK's commitments under SDGs 7 and 13.

On this front the main scope of TS-HVDC project was to pursue the development and validation of an advanced, hierarchical coordinated control strategy. This strategy integrated several novel control functions aimed at improving system response during and after fault events. These included: (1) an FRT function implemented in GFL converters (both HVDC and wind farm inverters), designed to reduce fault-induced transient currents and protect the system under stress and (2) an active power–frequency droop control scheme implemented in GFM converters and coordinated with GFL devices for active power curtailment during post-fault recovery.

The primary objectives are the following:

- (i) to experimentally validate the proposed control strategy using power hardware-in-the-loop (PHIL) testing,(ii) to increase the technology readiness level (TRL) of the control methodology by testing it under realistic operating conditions
- (ii) to formally document the findings in a peer-reviewed scientific journal, thereby contributing to the body of research on transient stability and control in offshore grid systems.

The test lab set-up will be presented in the following sections.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The structure of this document is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the state of the art related to the project, outlining current challenges and limitations in integrating offshore wind farms with multi-infeed HVDC systems. Section 3 presents the test plan and methodology, detailing the developed simulation model, testing setup, and data management approach. Section 4 summarizes the results, provides an in-depth explanation of the developed control algorithm, and showcases its performance across various scenarios. Finally, Section 5 discusses open issues identified during the project and offers suggestions for future work and improvements in system control and design.

2 State-of-the-Art/State-of-Technology

The European Union’s net-zero target for 2050 has accelerated the integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into power systems. However, the RES hosting capacity in many countries has reached its limit due to technical, spatial, legal, and financial constraints. To address this, subsea HVDC interconnections have emerged as a key enabler for flexible, large-scale RES integration—especially offshore wind power. Offshore HVDC-connected wind farms offer a practical solution to spatial limitations and the need for extended inter-area power transfers, forming the backbone of evolving offshore transmission networks.

The most commonly encountered topologies for offshore wind farm interconnection via HVDC links to the main grid are the multi-infeed AC networks with HVDC links and multi-terminal HVDC and the, whose schematics are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.**, respectively. These systems are central to strategic plans like the UK’s Holistic Network Design (HND), which envisions more than 20 GW of offshore wind integrated via multiple multi-infeed offshore hubs in the North Sea. Similar initiatives are underway in Germany, Denmark, and the Netherlands.

Figure 1: Typical structure of multi-infeed AC system with HVDC links

Figure 2: Typical structure of multi-terminal HVDC link

The control of HVDC systems—especially in modular multilevel converter (MMC) based HVDC systems—has seen significant advancements. Several recent studies have explored:

- **Voltage and frequency control schemes** for stable operation under low wind scenarios and improved start-up reliability.
- **Fault-ride-through (FRT) and post-fault recovery mechanisms**, particularly in VSC-HVDC systems and wind farm interfaces.
- **Advanced voltage modulation and droop control** techniques to manage power flow and system dynamics under abnormal conditions

In particular, extensive research efforts have been devoted to enhancing power control schemes within multi-terminal HVDC (MT-HVDC) systems to support both offshore wind integration and regional interconnections. Notably, several studies have proposed innovative control strategies targeting active power optimization in offshore Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC) stations [1]. These strategies adjust the offshore AC voltage to enable efficient wind power transfer via Diode Rectifier (DR)-based HVDC links, particularly under low wind conditions, thereby minimizing transmission losses. Other research has focused on startup procedures and frequency support mechanisms using MMC-HVDC systems, aiming to improve transient frequency stability and ensure smooth system activation. Fault-ride-through (FRT) control schemes have also been a subject of investigation, emphasizing the need for coordinated control between wind farms and VSC-HVDC systems during and after faults. A prominent example is North China's multi-terminal VSC-HVDC grid project [2], which utilises a hybrid voltage control approach—combining steady-state optimization and emergency response—validated through simulation. In addressing fault-induced DC overvoltages, researchers have proposed dynamic frequency setpoint increases, AC voltage reduction via PI control, and converter locking strategies to mitigate power imbalances during AC faults.

Despite significant progress in multi-terminal HVDC links, interest has also been raised towards multi-infeed AC offshore island systems, due to their greater potential for enhancing energy connectivity across regions and facilitating grid planning and market integration. Multi-infeed AC systems are particularly effective in integrating diverse energy sources spread across different geographic locations into a unified grid. This capability not only supports more robust and flexible grid planning but also enhances market integration by enabling a more efficient and reliable distribution of electricity across various markets. Furthermore, These systems present fewer interoperability challenges compared to multi-terminal systems involving multiple vendors. The studies presented in [3] investigate the control interactions and interferences in a multi-infeed HVDC system with two converters. The phenomenon is studied in the frequency domain by using the admittance-based stability assessment. Harmonic stability under different network characteristics is addressed, focusing only on dynamics in the AC system and neglecting dynamics of DC side. The researchers in references [4-8] examined a coordinated control strategy aimed at reducing LCC-HVDC commutation failures within a hybrid multi-infeed HVDC system. Specifically, the authors of [9] leveraged the reactive power support of the VSC-HVDC for the receiving AC system, assessing the required reactive power post-fault based on the extinguishing angle or area, and integrating this data into the reactive control link of the VSC-HVDC inverter. This integration enhances the LCC-HVDC's capacity to alleviate commutation failures. Meanwhile, the authors of [10] utilised the commutation failure immunity index to gauge the robustness of a hybrid multi-infeed HVDC system against such failures, analyzing how different control modes of VSC-HVDC affect LCC-HVDC commutation failure. They presented coordinated control methods between VSC-HVDC and LCC-HVDC that reduce LCC-HVDC commutation failures and improve the system's fault recovery capabilities during and after disturbances. Additionally, Reference [8] discusses a reactive power management method for a multi-infeed HVDC system in Korea.

Despite these advances, multi-infeed AC offshore island systems remain underexplored

compared to their multi-terminal HVDC counterparts. Research on multi-infeed HVDC systems has largely concentrated on AC offshore islands, with a primary focus on optimal power distribution and system operations under typical and AC-disturbed conditions. Despite significant progress in multi-terminal HVDC research, multi-infeed AC offshore island systems remain relatively underexplored. Most existing literature concentrates on aspects such as AC-side harmonic stability, startup procedures, and commutation failure mitigation in hybrid VSC–LCC HVDC systems. However, these studies do not adequately address severe DC fault scenarios, including complete disconnection of HVDC links, which pose a critical threat to system stability and operational continuity. Another key limitation is that most existing research is confined to simulation-based validation, which, while valuable, lacks the depth of insight that can be obtained through real-time testing using actual converter hardware. As a result, practical challenges related to control implementation, hardware interoperability, and dynamic system recovery during faults remain to be addressed.

On that front, TS-HVDC was designed specifically to address these critical gaps in the state-of-the-art. The project focused on the real-time experimental validation of novel hierarchical coordinated control strategies for post-fault management and FRT in multi-infeed AC offshore islands. The validation involved:

- Power hardware-in-the-loop (PHIL) experimentation using actual GFL hardware.
- Assessment of coordinated control responses during simulated AC and DC faults.
- Integration of advanced control functions including droop control, DC overvoltage management, and master-setpoint dispatching.

By combining real-time hardware experimentation with the developed control logic, TS-HVDC delivered a comprehensive validation of operational resilience in multi-infeed offshore systems. It directly contributes to the technical feasibility of upcoming European offshore grid plans and helps derisk practical implementation aligned with HND goals

3 Executed Tests and Experiments

3.1 Test Plan, Standards, Procedures, and Methodology

The main goal of this project was to validate a sophisticated coordinated control strategy that orchestrates various advanced control functions. The strategy is specifically designed to ensure system stability and effectively addresses challenges associated with post-fault recovery in multi-infeed AC offshore island configurations, featuring HVDC links operating in both GFM and GFL modes, as well as offshore wind farms.

Building on the User Group member's experience on FRT functions, GFM, and GFL concepts, the team has developed a hierarchical and coordinated control strategy which leverages advanced existing control functions and by applying adequate interventions, enhance FRT capabilities and post-fault stability of AC offshore power islands, which are comprised of GFL and GFM converters. Specifically, the developed control strategy includes the following novel interventions:

- **Control functions 1:** FRT control function which has been implemented in the converters of the wind farms and the HVDC link operating in GFL mode. The adopted FRT approach involves reducing the active and reactive currents during faults, effectively mitigating any transient disturbances caused during AC and DC faults and limiting current and voltage stresses in the weak AC network of the offshore power island.
- **Control functions 2:** Active power/frequency droop control has been implemented in the GFM converter. The frequency signal serves as an indicator activating the corresponding active power/frequency droop control in the GFL HVDC converters and the wind farm GFL converters during the post-fault period. An active power curtailment philosophy has been implemented in the wind farms to help the system recover during events that could lead to imbalances in active power distribution between pre-fault and post-fault periods, such as the disconnection of an HVDC link. This strategy helps maintain power balance within the AC offshore island, prevents power excess, maintains the power target at the point of interconnection, and mitigates system stresses while staying within the capacity limits of the units.
- **Control function 3:** The developed strategy proposes the incorporation of a master controller which dispatches the appropriate control setpoints to the units operating in P-Q control mode aiding in restoring the system to its pre-fault power dispatch or to new stable operating points for scenarios that an asset has been disconnected due to sustained fault conditions.

Test plan

The work for this project was conducted in two stages: a) a pre-visit stage carried out in December 2024 which involved receipt of a multi-terminal HVDC network model and adaptation to the system network shown in Figure 4 and b) an on-site stage during which the hardware equipment including the power amplifier (Cinergia), the converter control and hardware prototyping platform (Imperix) and a real-time simulator (OPAL-RT) were used in a power-hardware-in-the-loop setup to implement and validate the developed control strategy for disturbances in multi-infeed AC offshore island configurations. A summary of the conducted activities is provided in the table below followed by a more analytical description of each task.

Phase	Activity	Description
1. Pre-visit	Network model adaptation	Modification of provided baseline MATLAB/Simulink model
	Event testing (offline)	Tested system under AC and DC fault scenarios offline
	Control model preparation	Integration of FRT and droop control logic into Imperix model
2. Initial Set-up (on-site)	Lab induction	Introduction to TecNALIA facilities, equipment, and procedures
	Hardware overview	Familiarisation with Cinergia amplifier, Imperix equipment, OPAL-RT platform
	Code refinement and real-time testing	Upload of converter control model to Imperix and modification for real-time compatibility
3. PHIL Integration	Real-time network model adaptation	Incorporation of OPAL-RT interfacing blocks in the Simulink model
	Steady-state validation	Verification of OPAL-RT model and established hardware interface
	PHIL connection	Formation of the PHIL set-up including cinergia, Imperix and OPAL-RT
4. Testing and Validation	Set-up of simulation events	Application of AC/DC faults on the network and final parameterisation
	Real-time testing	Final testing and validation of proposed method
	Data acquisition	Collection of data records for final simulation cases

Preparation Phase (Prior to Arrival at Tecalia)

A detailed network model was received in MATLAB/Simulink format, serving as the baseline for the testing campaign. The User Group modified this model to include:

- Two HVDC links: one operating in grid-forming mode and one in grid-following mode (1000MW each). Both links are designed as symmetrical monopoles.
- Two offshore wind farms, each with a rated power output of 1000 MW, both operating in grid-following mode.

Afterwards, extensive offline simulations were conducted to validate the performance of the modified model under both AC and DC fault scenarios. This ensured the model's fitness for real-time testing and verified the appropriate implementation of the fault ride-through and droop control concepts which comprise the developed method.

In addition, a typical converter control model for Imperix hardware was also received. This was expanded to include the custom droop logic developed as part of the TS-HVDC control strategy. Offline tests were performed to pre-validate the converter response and minimize debugging during the hardware integration phase.

On-site PHIL testing at Tecalia

Upon arrival at Tecalia, the User Group received comprehensive inductions on laboratory safety, the available hardware equipment, and PHIL system setup, including:

- **Hardware Overview:**
 - Cinergia power amplifier
 - Imperix control and prototyping platform
 - OPAL-RT real-time simulator

Following this, the testing activities proceeded as outlined:

1. Model Integration and Preparation:

- a. Uploaded the pre-prepared Simulink converter control code onto the Imperix platform.
- b. Performed necessary final adjustments using Imperix library blocks to ensure compatibility with real-time operation.
- c. Integrated the Imperix converter with the OPAL-RT simulation environment using PHIL interfaces.

2. System Setup and Steady-State Validation:

- a. Modified the offline Simulink model to include OPAL-RT interfacing blocks, with support from the Tecalia team.

- b. Ran the OPAL-RT model independently to verify steady-state performance before connecting any physical hardware.
- c. Established and validated PHIL connectivity, with the GFM converter (within the OPAL-RT model) providing reference voltage and frequency to the physical GFL converter (Imperix) interfaced through the power amplifier.

3. Real-Time Testing and Disturbance Scenarios:

- a. Conducted normal operation tests to confirm proper synchronization and baseline behavior.
- b. Introduced a series of fault conditions including:
 - i. AC faults of varying duration and location
 - ii. DC faults on HVDC links
 - iii. Disconnection of one or both HVDC links
- c. Assessed the response of the droop control logic and the converter behavior under transient events.

4. Data Acquisition and Analysis:

- a. Collected detailed results from each test scenario, focusing on current, voltage, frequency, and power responses.
- b. Verified the system's ability to maintain post-fault stability and dynamic performance as per the TS-HVDC objectives.
- c. These results will support the production of a scientific journal publication and contribute towards increasing the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the proposed solution.

3.2 Test Set-up

To validate the above-described control strategies, a power hardware-in-the-loop (PHIL) simulation setup was utilized. This phase aimed to assess the performance of these strategies under real-world conditions, using actual hardware of control devices and converters, identifying any potential needs for improvements and limitations.

The testing set-up is illustrated in Figure 3. It is designed to progressively validate the coordinated control strategy for multi-infeed AC offshore islands, integrated through HVDC systems and offshore wind farms through a comprehensive assessment of the control strategy under different fault conditions and hardware configurations.

Figure 3 PHIL experimentation of Grid-following inverter

Figure 4 Modelling of the offshore AC island with HVDC infeeds at MATLAB/Simulink towards real-time simulation at OPAL-RT

Particularly, for the use case of this project, two HVDC links operating in both GFM and GFL

modes are simulated within a MATLAB/Simulink environment, executed in real-time at the OPAL-RT device, as shown in Figure 4. Then, a single GFL converter in the hardware with capacity of 15kW and connected to 230V, interfaced to the simulation model through a power amplifier, as shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 5: Project set-up with with cinergia amplifier and Opal-RT environment

Figure 6: Connection of Imperix

It is noteworthy that the high voltage network in the simulation environment, is appropriately interfaced with the low-voltage hardware setup through the required interface mechanism. This setup allows for the dynamic interaction between the physical hardware and the simulated environment, even if the voltage and power ratings of the hardware converter are scaled down. In more detail, both DC and AC faults can be realized through the simulated environment, and the response of a hardware GFL converter is tested and all the developed control algorithms are verified.

The testing procedure for this use case includes:

- Establish the appropriate interconnections and interfacing between the hardware setup and the OPAL-RT simulation platform, utilizing state-of-the-art PHIL interfacing mechanisms.
- Program the GFL converter through the Simulink embedded coder for Imperix converters and model the rest of the control and power components through the Simulink interface of the OPAL-RT simulator.
- Initialise the PHIL setup through a dummy load and then proceed to interconnection of the GFL converter into the setup.
- Validating the control strategy response during simulated DC and AC faults.
- Recording currents and voltages on both AC and DC sides during tests to ensure that all specifications and control functions perform as expected.

Through the above testing procedure, the project aims to enhance the TRL of the proposed solution, demonstrating its efficacy and readiness for broader application and informing future research publications and grant proposals, filling the research gap in the transient stability of multi-infeed AC offshore islands.

3.3 Data Management and Processing

The data management and processing strategy for the TS-HVDC project was centered around capturing detailed dynamic and steady-state measurements from both the OPAL-RT real-time simulator and the Imperix hardware converter. During the simulations, data from the main AC bus of the multi-infeed AC network were recorded in the OPAL-RT model (via RT-LAB relevant functions), including active and reactive power, AC bus voltage, instantaneous voltages and currents at various points in the system, as well as RMS voltages and measurements. These datasets were exported as mat files using the RT-Lab software. Similarly, for the Imperix hardware converter data comprising equivalent voltage, current, and power measurements were captured through the associated plotting hardware and stored in .csv format. Preliminary data checks and visualizations were carried out on-site using MATLAB's plotting tools. Following the testing, all data were further processed using Python-based routines to enable detailed post-analysis and final result visualisation.

4 Results and Conclusions

4.1 Discussion of Results

This section summarises the results obtained for the lab access along with a high level description of the developed algorithm and the testing set-up.

4.1.1 Developed algorithm

This work introduces a hierarchical coordinated control strategy designed to ensure the stability and active power balance of multi-infeed AC offshore islands integrated via HVDC links. The proposed strategy effectively addresses challenges associated with transient events—particularly AC and DC faults—and supports improved system recovery following such disturbances. By integrating advanced control functions and enabling precise, targeted interventions, the approach enhances both fault response and post-fault operational performance, thereby increasing the overall reliability of these configurations.

The proposed strategy consists of two core control components:

- **Fault Ride Through (FRT) control**

Fault ride-through capability is a critical requirement for modern power systems, allowing them to remain connected and operational during transient fault conditions without tripping generation units. This capability contributes significantly to system resilience, minimises operational disruptions, and ensures faster recovery from disturbances—thereby reducing both downtime and associated economic impacts.

In this work, FRT functionality has been implemented in the GFL converters of the HVDC links. The strategy is based on suppressing both active and reactive current injection during fault conditions, thereby mitigating the impact of transients and limiting voltage and current stress on the offshore island's inherently weak AC network.

Specifically, when the measured grid voltage falls below 0.85 pu of the nominal voltage, the FRT function is triggered. At this point, the reference values for the direct-axis and quadrature-axis currents (i_d , i_q) are set to zero. This immediate curtailment is essential to maintaining network stability by preventing power imbalances during faults, which could otherwise escalate into broader system disturbances.

- **P/f droop-control**

To address post-fault power imbalances—particularly those caused by HVDC link disconnections during export mode—a coordinated active power/frequency (P/f) droop control mechanism is employed. The GFM converter defines the system frequency, and deviations in this frequency serve as input signals to activate the corresponding P/f droop response in the GFL converters.

An active power curtailment scheme is embedded in the GFL converters to assist system recovery when an active power surplus arises. Such conditions commonly occur following the loss of an HVDC link in exporting power mode, leading to a mismatch between generation and consumption on the offshore island.

The P/f droop control law for the GFL converters is expressed as:

$$\Delta P = K_D \times (\omega_{nominal} - \omega_{PLL})$$

Where:

- ΔP is the corrective reference signal for the GFL active power controller,
- K_D is the droop gain, adjusted based on the pre-disturbance active power dispatch,
- $\omega_{nominal}$ is the nominal angular frequency,
- ω_{PLL} is the frequency measured by the PLL of the GFL converter (in rad/s).

This formulation allows the GFL units to reduce active power output proportionally in response to frequency increases caused by power surpluses.

For the GFM converter, the frequency is determined as:

$$\omega_{GFM} = \omega_{nominal} + K_{PGFM} \times P_{measGFM} \times 2 \times \pi$$

Where:

- $P_{measGFM}$ is the measured active power output of the GFM converter,
- K_{PGFM} is the droop gain of the GFM converter.

The GFM unit thereby defines system frequency as a function of its active power export, ensuring synchronization across the network.

Given the GFL converters synchronise their frequency via PLL, ω_{PLL} converges to ω_{GFM} under normal conditions. This reflects the core principle of the proposed strategy. A fundamental aspect of this strategy involves dynamically adjusting the K_D P/f droop gain of GFL converter according to the current active power dispatch in the network. The selection of the droop gain is crucial for maintaining stability especially during worst case event (i.e., disconnection of one HVDC link in exporting mode operating in full power). In such events, the active power reference for the GFL converters is strategically curtailed to a level that restores and maintains the power balance on the offshore island, ensuring the system's resilience.

To distinguish between normal operation and transient conditions affecting the power balance, the P/f droop control in the GFM converter is only activated within a specified deadband—between 1 pu (nominal capacity) and 1.2 pu (thermal limit) of the GFM unit. Active power output within this range is interpreted as a signal of potential asset loss or imbalance on the offshore network. GFM output power falling within this range serves as a critical indicator of either asset loss or an imbalance in the power distribution on the offshore island, triggering the necessary droop control functionality to address these issues.

4.1.2 Simulation results

The results presented in this section have been selected to showcase two typical examples of characteristic events that demonstrate the validation of the proposed fault management algorithm. In particular, the events include:

- A DC fault applied to one of the HVDC links, where the offshore converter operates in GFL control mode and in export mode. This fault causes the disconnection of the HVDC link.
- A solid three-phase AC fault applied at the common bus of the HVDC link, which does not lead to the disconnection of any unit.

These selected scenarios aim to demonstrate the effectiveness, sensitivity, and robustness of the proposed algorithms.

It should be noted that when an HVDC link operates in *export mode* (indicated by a negative sign in active power), it supplies active power from the offshore AC island to the main grid. Conversely, in *import mode* (positive active power), the HVDC link absorbs active power from the main grid into the offshore AC island.

Results of DC fault

This scenario examines the effectiveness of the developed algorithm during a pole-to-pole DC fault with offshore converter GFL2), which occurs at $t = 183.3$ s and results in the disconnection of the HVDC-2 link within 250 ms. Prior to the fault, the system was operating at maximum capacity: HVDC-1 (GFL1 converter) and HVDC-3 (GFL3 converter) were each importing 1.2 GW, HVDC-2 (GFL2 converter) was exporting 1.2 GW, and an additional 1.2 GW was being exported by the HVDC link with the GFM converter, which operates as the power balancer.

Upon fault occurrence, HVDC-1 and HVDC-3 initiated FRT control, reducing their output to zero to alleviate stress on the offshore AC island. Within 250 ms, HVDC-2 was disconnected, resulting in a power surplus of 1.2 GW—equivalent to the nominal capacity of the GFM unit.

This sudden surplus triggered the P/f droop response of the GFM unit, causing an increase in system frequency and activating the corresponding P/f droop control in both GFL1 and GFL3. The activation of droop control in the GFM unit led to its overloading, with its power export reaching 1.44 GW (exceeding its thermal limit of 1.2 pu). As the frequency continued to rise, the P/f droop control in the GFL1 and GFL3 converters was engaged, resulting in curtailment of their output to 0.72 GW each in order to stabilise the system. The same droop gain was applied to both GFL1 and GFL3.

Figure 6 illustrates the active power output of all units and demonstrates the successful rebalancing of system power. Figure 7 shows the frequency response, and Figure 8 presents the voltage at the common AC bus. The frequency reaches 51.5 Hz due to the overload condition on the GFM unit, serving as a key indicator for the P/f droop response in GFL1 and GFL3. As observed, the system voltage at the offshore AC island quickly returns to steady state once power rebalancing is achieved after the fault event.

Figure 6: Active power of all units – DC fault

Figure 7: Frequency of the system – DC fault

Figure 8: Instantaneous voltage at the common AC bus – DC fault

Results of AC fault

This scenario examines a solid three-phase-to-ground AC fault at the offshore AC island, under the same pre-fault conditions as described in the previous scenario. The fault occurs at $t = 98.11$ s and lasts for 300 ms. It does not lead to the disconnection of any assets, and the network's active power dispatch remains unchanged throughout the event.

During the fault, GFL-1, GFL-2, and GFL-3 exhibit FRT capability. Once the fault is cleared, all units promptly recover to their pre-fault power levels. Figure 9 shows the active power outputs of all units, while Figure 10 illustrates the system voltage at the common AC bus. As observed, the system is quickly restored following fault clearance.

This scenario demonstrates the effectiveness of the FRT control. It confirms that limiting the current during the fault facilitates rapid system recovery and enhances overall system stability. Additionally, it highlights the discriminative nature of the proposed control strategy, which remains inactive during AC faults that do not affect the active power dispatch.

Figure 9: Active power of all units – AC fault

Figure 10: Instantaneous voltage at the common AC bus – AC fault

4.2 Conclusions

This work presents a coordinated control strategy aimed at enhancing the stability of multi-infeed AC offshore islands connected via HVDC links. The proposed approach integrates and extends existing control mechanisms—such as FRT and P/f droop control—to address the specific stability challenges that arise during transient disturbances. The strategy is particularly focused on DC faults occurring during export-mode operation, which can lead to sudden power surpluses and pose a risk to overall system stability.

While previous studies have explored the operation of such systems, the work presented here uniquely addresses the severe impact of transient events and offers a targeted solution for their management. Notably, there is currently no evidence of other fault management strategies for such systems that have been validated through real-time testing.

Simulation results show that during events leading to power surpluses, the proposed droop mechanism is promptly activated, enabling controlled overloading of GFM unit and curtailment of GFL units to stabilise the system. This ensures safe system recovery across a range of operating conditions. Additionally, the response to AC faults demonstrates the strategy's robustness and selective activation, remaining inactive when no surplus occurs, thus avoiding unnecessary power curtailment. The employed FRT strategy also proven effective in minimising active and reactive currents during faults, which is critical for fault survival in these inherently weak network configurations.

Real-time testing and thorough evaluation of the algorithm confirmed its applicability to real-world systems, paving the way for wider adoption of offshore AC islands interconnected by HVDC links through the mitigation of key operational challenges.

5 Open Issues and Suggestions for Improvements

Future work should focus on the implementation of the proposed control algorithm in systems with a higher number of grid-forming (GFM) units, in order to evaluate its scalability and effectiveness under more complex configurations. Additionally, further development and deployment of the master controller are recommended, enabling it to dynamically dispatch appropriate set-points—such as active and reactive power and control modes—to coordinate system components and facilitate a smooth transition to a new steady state following disturbances.

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